

Effect of sodium carbonate on some properties of magnesia cement

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Manuscript received 31 March 1998, revised 2 August 2000, accepted 12 February 2001

Incorporation of sodium carbonate in magnesia cement affects setting process differently but improves strength and durability of the product.

Magnesia cement (Sorel's cement) has many superior properties to that of portland cement¹. The literature is silent about the effect of sodium carbonate on magnesia cement, hence the present investigation was undertaken. The basic reason behind this was that the anionic part forms inactive insoluble phases with active lime present in commercial magnesia, calcium chloride present in commercial magnesium chloride and other harmful impurities².

Results and Discussion

Table 1 reveals the effects of sodium carbonate (powder and saturated solution) as admixture on setting characteristics of magnesia cement. Trends in setting processes in both the cases are found different. In case of the powder, volume of the gauging solution required for standard consistency is found to increase slightly. This is probably due to the caustic nature of the powder which dissolves in the matrix exothermically and requires extra water in form of the gauging solution. Hence some extra gauging solution is required to prepare the wet-mix of the comparable consistency. Decreasing trend in the setting time with increasing proportions of sodium carbonate powder is attributed to simultaneous formation of basic magnesium carbonate – a rapid forming solid phase. In case of saturated solution of the additive, initial decrease in amount of the gauging solution is attributed to inactivation of active lime and

reduced hydrophilic tendency of sodium carbonate (because now it is in solution form). With further increase in the amounts of sodium carbonate solution, a definite proportion of magnesium chloride is converted into basic magnesium carbonate. Initial setting periods in case of saturated solution of the additive are found almost constant (130 ± 5 min). Plausible reason for this is that both the solutions (sodium carbonate solution as additive and magnesium chloride solution as gauging solution) contribute almost in the same way to the factors responsible for initial setting (sol formation and hydration). However, final setting periods are found to increase with increasing amounts of the additive. Probable reason for this may be that incorporation of sodium carbonate in the gauging solution causes formation of almost indifferent solid phase of basic magnesium carbonate (eq. 5). Thus amount of magnesium chloride available free is reduced. This reduces the formation of magnesium oxychloride (strength-giving composition responsible for final setting). Inactivation of active lime, reduced exothermicity and slowed-down setting process contribute to the observed glossiness of the surface and are responsible for insignificant volume change of the trial blocks.

Table 1. Effect of sodium carbonate (powder and saturated solution) on setting characteristics of magnesia cement

Gauging solution : 22° Be', Dry-mix composition : 1 : 2 (inert filler), Temp. = 30°, humidity = 75%

Parameter	Composition of dry-mix (% Additive, w/w)					Composition of dry-mix (% Additive, v/v)				
	0	5	10	15	20	0	5	10	15	20
Volume of g.s. (ml)	55	60	61	61	61	55	54	58	73	75
Initial setting time (min)	180	150	130	130	90	180	125	130	125	135
Final setting time (min)	300	285	260	250	200	300	305	310	320	325
Nature of blocks :	Glossy, with slight volume expansion					Glossy, with insignificant volume expansion				

Table 2. Effect of sodium carbonate (powder and saturated solution) on weathering of magnesia cement

Gauging solution : 22° Be', Dry-mix composition : 1 : 2 (inert filler), Curing : air drying, Temp. = 30°

Observations	Composition of dry-mix (% Additive, w/w)					Composition of dry-mix (% Additive, v/v)				
	0	5	10	15	20	0	5	10	15	20
Weight after 24 h (g)	275	263	265	255	250	275	275	273	390	393
Weight after 7 d (g)	255	267	275	260	260	255	254	255	368	366
Weight after 30 d (g)	270	255	258	257	258	270	365	270	370	368

exothermicity in case of the powder as an additive suggest the simultaneous formation of basic magnesium carbonate, alkaline hydroxides and magnesium oxychloride cementing compositions. The former two materials are hygroscopic and have tendency to absorb acidic gases like carbon dioxide, sulfur dioxide, etc. from the atmosphere rapidly. At the same time, slow evaporation of uncombined moisture also continues. Consequently, it is noted that weight of trial blocks first increases and then decreases due to secondary effect. In case of the saturated solution as an additive, the trends are slightly changed. Reduced exothermicity and slow setting in this case leave a lot of moisture uncombined even after setting. Thus it is noted that weight of trial blocks decreases with time due to evaporation of this uncombined water. However, magnesium chloride in the gauging solution reacts with the added sodium carbonate solution. This leaves a lot of magnesia unreacted and uncombined in the matrix. Thus uncombined magnesia and basic magnesium carbonate (eq. 7) slowly absorb acidic gases (CO₂, SO₂ etc.) from the atmosphere. Hence initial decrease in weight followed by an increase is expected.

Table 2 shows the effect of sodium carbonate (powder and saturated solution) as additives on weathering of magnesia cement trial blocks. Decreasing setting periods and high

Effects of sodium carbonate (powder and saturated solution) on moisture ingress in the trial blocks were studied.

Table 3. Effect of sodium carbonate (powder and saturated solution) on soundness of magnesia cement

Gauging solution : 22° Be', Dry-mix composition : 1 : 2 (inert filler), Curing : air drying, Temp. = 30°

Sl. Parameter no.	Composition of dry-mix (% Additive, w/w)					Composition of dry-mix (% Additive, v/v)				
	0	5	10	15	20	0	5	10	15	20
1. Weight of cement composition (g)										
(i) Magnesia	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13
(ii) Dolomite	26	24.7	23.4	22.1	20.8	26	26	26	26	26
(iii) Additive (g/ml)	Nil	1.3	2.6	3.9	5.2	Nil	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0
2. Use of MgCl ₂ solution (ml)	11.5	10	10	12	13	11.5	9.5	9	8.5	8
3. Distance between two pointers before starting (cm)	1.8	1.6	1.6	2.5	1.4	1.8	2.5	3	1.4	2.4
4. Distance between two pointers after 7 days (cm)	2.0	1.8	1.7	2.4	1.5	2.0	2.5	3	1.5	2.5
5. Time (h) in water at 27–32°	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48	48
6. Distance between two pointers before boiling (cm)	2.2	1.9	1.7	1.8	1.5	2.2	2.5	3.1	1.5	2.5
7. Distance after boiling (cm)	2.3	1.9	1.7	1.8	1.6	2.3	2.5	3.1	1.5	2.5
8. Expansion of cement (cm)	0.1	0	0	0	0	0.1	0	0	0	0

Inactivation of harmful impurities like active lime and calcium chloride and simultaneous formation of inert solid phases as mentioned above on incorporation of solid sodium carbonate, reduces moisture ingress remarkably. However, this effect is less in case of its saturated solution as an additive. This is attributed to the decreasing proportion of available magnesium chloride in the gauging solution responsible for cement formation in the latter case. The above discussion is supported by the compressive strength data. It is noted that compressive strength increases slightly with increasing proportion of sodium carbonate (powder as well as solution), i.e. from 480 to 600 kg cm⁻² with 0 to 20% additive. This may owe to the inactivation of active lime, calcium chloride, etc. and formation of inter-crossing crystalline systems, like carbonates, basic carbonate, along-with the oxychloride.

The above hypothesis is supported further from the investigations on the effects of sodium carbonate (powder and saturated solution) as an additive on soundness of magnesia cement (Table 3). The results reveal almost insignificant volume changes in the trial blocks. This may be attributed to inactivation of materials like active lime, calcium chloride, etc. and conversion of free soluble magnesium carbonate, etc.

Experimental

Magnesia powder (about 200 mesh), dolomite powder (about 100 mesh) (both procured from M/s Shri Hari

Udyog Bharti, Alwar), magnesium chloride and sodium carbonate (B.D.H.) were used.

Procedures : Setting time⁵, weathering effect, moisture ingress (steam test)⁵, compressive strength^{4,5} and soundness test³⁻⁶ were evaluated by the standard procedures.

Acknowledgement

The authors owe much to Principal, Mr. S. R. Saini for facilities and to Mr. I. C. Tiwari, Dr. T. N. Ojha, P. S. Joshi and A. Ali for their valuable suggestions.

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